

The definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions and its properties

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Abstract: This article aims to study the definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions and its properties. The definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions are defined in this study, and a set of theories are presented, including the Fundamental theorem of 2- refined neutrosophic integral calculus, the mean-value theorem of 2- refined neutrosophic integral calculus with its two parts, in addition to the properties of the definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions. Also, we used the n-Refined AH-Isometry [11].

Keywords: definite integrals; 2- refined neutrosophic functions; properties; mean-value theorem.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

As an alternative to the existing logics, Smarandache proposed the neutrosophic logic to represent a mathematical model of uncertainty, vagueness, ambiguity, imprecision, undefined, unknown, incompleteness, inconsistency, redundancy, contradiction, where Smarandache made refined neutrosophic numbers available in the following form: $(a, b_1I_1, b_2I_2, \dots, b_nI_n)$ where $a, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n \in R$ or C [1]. Agboola introduced the concept of refined neutrosophic algebraic structures [2]. In addition, the refined neutrosophic rings I was studied in paper [3], where it assumed that I splits into two indeterminacies I_1 [contradiction (true (T) and false (F))] and I_2 [ignorance (true (T) or false (F))]. Abobala presented the papers on some special substructures of refined neutrosophic rings and a study of ah-substructures in n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces [6-7].

Alhasan.Y and Abdulfatah. R also presented a study on the division of refined neutrosophic number [8].

There are papers presented in n-Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics, Neutrosophic Rings I [4-5] and studying the integral calculus according to the logic of neutrosophic by presenting a set of papers on that [9-10].

In addition, the AH-Isometry was extended to n-Refined AH-Isometry by Smarandache & Abobala in 2024 [11]

2. The definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions

Theorem 1 (Fundamental theorem of 2- refined neutrosophic integral calculus)

Let be $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ a continuous 2- refined neutrosophic function defined in $[a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, and let $F(x, I_1, I_2)$ be the anti-derivative of $f(x, I_1, I_2)$, that is

$$\int f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = F(x, I_1, I_2)$$

then:

$$\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = F(a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2) - F(b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2)$$

Where a, a_1, a_2, b, b_1, b_2 are real number, I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

Example 1

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \int_{-2+I_1-I_2}^{5-I_1+I_2} (-3I_1 + 2x)dx &= [-3I_1x + x^2]_{-2+I_1-I_2}^{5-I_1+I_2} \\ &= [-3I_1(5 - I_1 + I_2) + (5 - I_1 + I_2)^2] - [3I_1(-2 + I_1 - I_2) + (-2 + I_1 - I_2)^2] \\ &= -15I_1 + 25 - 11I_1 + 12I_2 - 6I_1 - 4 + 5I_1 - 5I_2 \\ &= 21 - 27I_1 + 7I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (2) \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}+\pi I_1+\pi I_2} \cos\left(x - \pi I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2\right) dx &= \left[\sin\left(x - \pi I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2\right)\right]_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}+\pi I_1+\pi I_2} \\ &= \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \pi I_1 + \pi I_2 - \pi I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2\right)\right] - \left[\sin\left(-\pi I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2\right)\right] \\ &= \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{5\pi}{4}I_2\right)\right] - \left[\sin\left(-\pi I_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}I_2\right)\right] \\ &= \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) + I_1 \left[\sin\left(\frac{7\pi}{4}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{7\pi}{4}\right)\right] + I_2 \left[\sin\left(\frac{7\pi}{4}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)\right] - I_1 \left[\sin\left(-\frac{3\pi}{4}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)\right] - I_2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \\ &= 1 + \sqrt{2}I_1 + (-\sqrt{2} - 1)I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (3) \int_{2I_2}^{-2+I_1-I_2} -2x(4 - 2I_1 + 5I_2 - x^2)^2 dx &= \left[\frac{(4 - 2I_1 + 5I_2 - x^2)^3}{3}\right]_{2I_2}^{-2+I_1-I_2} \\ &= \left[\frac{(4 - 5I_1 + 4I_2 - (-2 + I_1 - I_2)^2)^3}{3}\right] - \left[\frac{(4 - 5I_1 + 4I_2 - (2I_2)^2)^3}{3}\right] \\ &= \left[\frac{(4 - 5I_1 + 4I_2 - 4 + 5I_1 - 5I_2)^3}{3}\right] - \left[\frac{(4 - 5I_1 + 4I_2 - 4I_2)^3}{3}\right] \\ &= \left[\frac{-1}{3}I_2\right] - \left[\frac{64}{3} - \frac{65}{3}I_1\right] = -\frac{64}{3} + \frac{65}{3}I_1 - \frac{1}{3}I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (4) \quad & \int_{5+29I_1+6I_2}^{2+26I_1+25I_2} \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x-1-2I_1-I_2}} dx = [\sqrt{x-1-2I_1-I_2}]_{5+29I_1+6I_2}^{2+26I_1+25I_2} \\
 & = \sqrt{2+26I_1+25I_2-1-2I_1-I_2} - \sqrt{5+29I_1+6I_2-1-2I_1-I_2} \\
 & = \sqrt{1+24I_1+24I_2} - \sqrt{4+27I_1+5I_2} \\
 & = 1+2I_1+4I_2-2-3I_1-2I_2 \\
 & = -1-I_1+2I_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2 (The mean- value theorem of 2- refined neutrosophic integral calculus_ part I)

If $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ is continuous on an interval, then we say that $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ has an anti- derivative on that interval. In specific, if $a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2$ is any point in the interval, then $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ defined by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^x f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] = f(x, I_1, I_2) \\
 (2) \quad & \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_x^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] = -f(x, I_1, I_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 2

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{\pi+\frac{\pi}{3}I_1+\frac{\pi}{6}I_2}^x (\tan^2 t + 2 - 3I_1 + 4I_2) dt \right] = \tan^2 x + 2 - 3I_1 + 4I_2 \\
 (2) \quad & \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{9-5I_1+7I_2}^x \sqrt{5I_1 t + 4I_2} dt \right] = \sqrt{5I_1 x + 4I_2} \\
 (3) \quad & \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_x^{-6+I_1-I_2} (5I_1 t^3 + I_2 t^2 + t - 2I_1 + 5I_2) dt \right] = -5I_1 x^3 - I_2 x^2 - x + 2I_1 - 5I_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Remarks 1

$$(1) \quad \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{g(x, I_1, I_2)} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] = f(g(x, I_1, I_2))g'(x, I_1, I_2)$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{g(x, I_1, I_2)} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] &= \frac{d}{dx} [F(g(x, I_1, I_2))] \\
 &= F'(g(x, I_1, I_2))g'(x, I_1, I_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= f(g(x, I_1, I_2))\acute{g}(x, I_1, I_2)$$

$$(2) \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{g(x, I_1, I_2)}^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] = -f(g(x, I_1, I_2))\acute{g}(x, I_1, I_2)$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{g(x, I_1, I_2)}^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] &= \frac{d}{dx} [-F(g(x, I_1, I_2))] \\ &= -\acute{F}(g(x, I_1, I_2))\acute{g}(x, I_1, I_2) \\ &= -f(g(x, I_1, I_2))\acute{g}(x, I_1, I_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$(3) \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{g_1(x, I_1, I_2)}^{g_2(x, I_1, I_2)} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] = f(g_2(x, I_1, I_2)) \acute{g}_2(x, I_1, I_2) - f(g_1(x, I_1, I_2)) \acute{g}_1(x, I_1, I_2)$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{g_1(x, I_1, I_2)}^{g_2(x, I_1, I_2)} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] &= \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{g_1(x, I_1, I_2)}^{0+0I_1+0I_2} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt + \int_{0+0I_1+0I_2}^{g_2(x, I_1, I_2)} f(t, I_1, I_2) dt \right] \\ &= f(g_2(x, I_1, I_2)) \acute{g}_2(x, I_1, I_2) - f(g_1(x, I_1, I_2)) \acute{g}_1(x, I_1, I_2) \end{aligned}$$

Example 3

$$(1) \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{1+I_1+I_2}^{\cos(x+\frac{\pi}{3}I_1+\pi I_2)} (t^3 - I_1 + 7I_2) dt \right] = -(\cos^3(x + \frac{\pi}{3}I_1 + \pi I_2) - I_1 + 7I_2) \sin(x + \frac{\pi}{3}I_1 + \pi I_2)$$

$$(2) \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{-9-I_1+6I_2}^{\sqrt{I_1+3I_2-5x}} (-8 + I_2 - t) dt \right] = (-8 + I_2 - \sqrt{I_1 + 3I_2 - 5x}) \frac{-5}{2\sqrt{I_1 + 3I_2 - 5x}}$$

$$(3) \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{\ln(x+4+I_1+I_2)}^{5+2I_1+I_2} t dt \right] = -\frac{1}{x + 4 + I_1 + I_2} \ln(x + 4 + I_1 + I_2)$$

$$(4) \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_{-7x+I_1+4I_2}^{6x^2-2I_1+I_2} \frac{2 - I_1 + I_2}{2t + I_1 + 3I_2} dt \right] = \frac{(2 - I_1 + I_2)x}{12x^2 - 4I_1 + 2I_2 + I_1 + 3I_2} + \frac{14 - 7I_1 + 7I_2}{-14x + 2I_1 + 8I_2 + I_1 + 3I_2}$$

Theorem 3 (The mean- value theorem of 2- refined neutrosophic integral calculus_ part II)

If $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ is continuous on a closed 2- refined interval $[a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$, then there is at least one point $x^* = x_0 + x_1I_1 + x_2I_2$ in $[a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2]$ such that:

$$\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = f(x^*, I_1, I_2)(b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2 - (a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2))$$

Example 4

If $f(x, I_1, I_2) = 4x + 5I_1$ let's find x^* that satisfy the mean-value theorem of f on $[2 + I_1 + 3I_2, 4 + I_1 + 5I_2]$.

$$\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = f(x^*, I_1, I_2)(b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2 - (a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2))$$

$$\int_{2+I_1+3I_2}^{4+I_1+5I_2} (4x + 5I_1)dx = (4x^* + 5I_1)(2 + 2I_2)$$

$$[2x^2 + 5I_1x]_{2+I_1+3I_2}^{4+I_1+5I_2} = (4x^* + 5I_1)(2 + 2I_2)$$

$$[2(4 + I_1 + 5I_2)^2 + 5I_1(4 + I_1 + 5I_2)] - [2(2 + I_1 + 3I_2)^2 + 5I_1(2 + I_1 + 3I_2)] = (4x^* + 5I_1)(2 + 2I_2)$$

$$24 + 22I_1 - 6I_2 = (4x^* + 5I_1)(2 + 2I_2)$$

$$4x^* + 5I_1 = \frac{24 + 36I_1 + 88I_2}{2 + 2I_2}$$

$$4x^* + 5I_1 = \frac{12 + 18I_1 + 44I_2}{1 + 0 + I_2}$$

$$4x^* + 5I_1 = 12 + 9I_1 + 16I_2$$

$$4x^* = 12 + 4I_1 + 16I_2$$

$$x^* = 3 + I_1 + 4I_2 \in [2 + I_1 + 3I_2, 4 + I_1 + 5I_2]$$

Example 5

If $f(x, I_1, I_2) = 9\sqrt{x}$ let's find x^* that satisfy the mean-value theorem of f on $[0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2, 1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2]$.

$$\int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = f(x^*, I_1, I_2)(b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2 - (a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2))$$

$$\int_{0+0I_1+0I_2}^{1+12I_1+3I_2} 9\sqrt{x} dx = 9(1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2)\sqrt{x^*}$$

$$[6x\sqrt{x}]_{0+0I_1+0I_2}^{1+12I_1+3I_2} = 9(1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2)\sqrt{x^*}$$

$$6(1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2)\sqrt{1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2} = 9(1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2)\sqrt{x^*}$$

$$\sqrt{x^*} = \frac{2\sqrt{1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2}}{3}$$

$$x^* = \frac{4(1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2)}{9} = \frac{4 + 48I_1 + 12I_2}{9}$$

$$x^* = \frac{4}{9} + \frac{16}{3}I_1 + \frac{4}{3}I_2 \in [0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2, 1 + 12I_1 + 3I_2]$$

3. Properties of the definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions

Let $f(x, I_1, I_2)$ and $g(x, I_1, I_2)$ then:

$$(1) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(t, I_1, I_2)dt$$

$$(2) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{c+c_1I_1+c_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx + \int_{c+c_1I_1+c_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx$$

where: $a + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 \leq c + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2 \leq b + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2$

$$(3) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = 0$$

$$(4) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = - \int_{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2}^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx$$

$$(5) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} (c + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2)f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = (c + c_1I_1 + c_2I_2) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx$$

$$(6) \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} [f(x, I_1, I_2) \pm g(x, I_1, I_2)]dx$$

$$= \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2)dx \pm \int_{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2}^{b+b_1I_1+b_2I_2} g(x, I_1, I_2)dx$$

$$(7) \int_{-(a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2)}^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2) dx$$

$$= \begin{cases} 2 \int_0^{a+a_1I_1+a_2I_2} f(x, I_1, I_2) dx & ; \text{if } f(x, I_1, I_2) \text{ is even function} \\ 0 & ; \text{if } f(x, I_1, I_2) \text{ is odd function} \end{cases}$$

Example 6

$$1) \int_{9+4I_1-7I_2}^{9+4I_1-7I_2} (t^3 + (1 + I_1 + 3I_2)t^2 - 12I_1 - 9I_2) dx = 0$$

$$2) \int_{-\pi-\frac{\pi}{12}I_1+\frac{\pi}{3}I_2}^{\pi+\frac{\pi}{12}I_1-\frac{\pi}{3}I_2} -7I_2 \sin^7 x \cos^6 x dx$$

Put: $f(x, I_1, I_2) = -7I_2 \sin^7 x \cos^6 x$, then:

$$f(-x, I_1, I_2) = -7I_2 \sin^7(-x) \cos^6(-x)$$

$$= -7I_2 (\sin(-x))^7 (\cos(-x))^6 = 7I_2 \sin^7 x \cos^6 x$$

$$= -f(x, I_1, I_2)$$

Hence $f(x, I)$ is odd function, so by property 7, we get:

$$\int_{-\pi-\frac{\pi}{12}I_1+\frac{\pi}{3}I_2}^{\pi+\frac{\pi}{12}I_1-\frac{\pi}{3}I_2} -7I_2 \sin^7 x \cos^6 x dx = 0$$

3. Conclusions

This paper introduced the concept of the definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions and its properties, by discussing a set of theorems related to the definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions, where these theorems were proven. Also, the properties of the definite integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic functions were studied, which facilitated finding the result of the integrals of 2- refined neutrosophic function faster and directly. In addition, the importance of this paper comes from the fact that it facilitates many studies in the field of the neutrosophic integrals calculate.

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References

[1] Smarandache, F., " (T,I,F)- Neutrosophic Structures", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol 8, pp. 3-10, 2015.

- [2] Agboola, A.A.A. "On Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol 10, pp. 99-101, 2015.
- [3] Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A., and Smarandache, F., "Refined Neutrosophic Rings I", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 2(2), pp. 77-81. 2020.
- [4] Smarandache, F., "n-Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics", Progress in Physics, USA, vol 4, pp. 143-146, 2013.
- [5] Agboola, A.A.A.; Akinola, A.D; Oyebola, O.Y., "Neutrosophic Rings I", Int. J. of Math. Comb., vol 4, pp.1-14, 2011.
- [6] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Refined Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5, pp. 59-66. 2020.
- [7] Abobala, M., "A Study of AH-Substructures in n-Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 9, pp.74-85. 2020.
- [8] Alhasan, Y., and Abdulfatah, R., "Division of refined neutrosophic numbers", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 60, pp. 1-5. 2023.
- [9] Alhasan, Y., "The neutrosophic integrals and integration methods", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Volume 43, pp. 290-301, 2021.
- [10] Alhasan, Y., " The neutrosophic integrals by partial fraction ", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Volume 44, pp. 290-301, 2021.
- [11] Smarandache, F., and Abobala, M., "Operations with n-Refined Literal Neutrosophic Numbers using the Identification Method and the n-Refined AH-Isometry", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Volume 70, pp. 350-358, 2024.

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